

STRENGTHENING EMERGENCY RESPONSE: ASSESSING THE COMBINED IMPACT OF HIGH THREAT EMERGENCY CARE (HTEC) AND HOSTILE ENVIRONMENT AWARENESS TRAINING (HEAT)

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the integration of High Threat Emergency Care (HTEC) and Hostile Environment Awareness Training (HEAT) in strengthening emergency response capabilities in high-risk environments. HTEC equips first responders with life-saving medical interventions, ensuring rapid care under volatile conditions, while HEAT fosters situational awareness, survival tactics, and risk mitigation strategies. Using a mixed-method approach, surveys and interviews were conducted among 44 participants from various professional backgrounds to assess their willingness to intervene, concerns about safety, and mindset shifts following training. Real-world simulations and case-based evaluations measured the effectiveness of integrating HTEC and HEAT principles. Findings indicate that 91% of respondents expressed readiness to intervene in crises, attributing increased confidence to hands-on training. However, 80% highlighted personal safety concerns, emphasizing the need for structured intervention protocols. Additionally, 86% agreed that shifting from passive waiting to proactive emergency response enhances operational efficiency in high-threat situations. This study underscores the critical role of continuous education, real-world simulations, and interdisciplinary collaboration in refining intervention strategies and creating safer, more resilient response frameworks. By integrating medical and tactical preparedness, these programs contribute to optimal emergency care and risk management in hostile environments.

Keywords: *Emergency Response, HTEC, HEAT, Training*

INTRODUCTION

Most rescue and medical personnel are trained to administer first aid to wounded victims, particularly in post-incident situations. These techniques are essential for law enforcement, military personnel, and emergency responders operating in austere environments. Smith (2014) emphasized that most Fire and Emergency Medical Service (EMS) responders do not simply stand by when lives are at risk. They recognize the urgency of providing immediate care, understand the risks involved, and consistently demonstrate a commitment to action, even in high-threat conditions.

However, according to the U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2008), it typically takes 10 to 15 minutes for first responders to arrive at an emergency scene. Standard protocol often requires waiting until an area is considered relatively safe before initiating rescue operations. This raises concerns regarding the effectiveness of the “stage and wait” approach, as in reality, no scene is entirely safe unless someone possesses both knowledge and courage to provide immediate aid before medical personnel arrive.

Historical data supports this urgency. The wound data and munitions effectiveness team (1970) study found that 90% of battlefield deaths occurred before designated medical care was provided 42% instantly, 26% within five minutes, and 16% within five to 20 minutes. This means 84% of fatalities occurred within 30 minutes of injury, emphasizing the critical need for rapid intervention in emergency situations.

The Marawi siege emphasized the necessity of HTEC and HEAT program in aiding both soldiers and civilians during urban conflict. Tactical medical response played a critical role in improving survival rates amid prolonged battles. The crisis underscored the need for rapid intervention, effective casualty care, and enhanced coordination between combat units and emergency responders (ASPI, 2019). This event underscores the necessity of effective emergency response systems during crisis scenarios.

Recognizing the need for enhanced preparedness, Callaway (2011) and colleagues examined tactical emergency casualty care training, which was provided to at least 68,213 first responders, including law enforcement, fire services, EMS personnel, and hospital-based providers. These numbers likely underestimate the total trained personnel, as grassroots programs and private-sector training efforts were not fully accounted for. In response to mass casualty events, Knudson (2016) and colleagues emphasized the importance of the “stop the bleed” campaign, advocating for rapid bleeding control to improve survival rates.

Given these findings, it is necessary to validate these reports and conduct a final assessment to determine their relevance to today’s emergency response system, ensuring that modern protocols effectively address high-threat scenarios and optimize rescue efforts.

A Review of Hostile Environment Awareness Training from 2017 to 2021

The HEAT programs conducted in 2021, 2019, and 2017 have played a significant role in enhancing emergency response preparedness in high-risk environments. Each year's training has adapted to evolving security challenges, refining methodologies to improve crisis intervention capabilities among civilians, professionals, and emergency responders.

According to Blyth et al. (2021), the increasing demand for HEAT stems from the humanitarian sector's exposure to volatile regions, necessitating structured duty-of-care measures. Organizations that fail to adequately train their personnel face potential litigation and reputational damage. Similarly, Lambert and Westwood (2019) examined the impact of high-risk conditions on South African emergency medical personnel, finding that 92% of surveyed students felt unsafe during clinical shifts. Their study supported the inclusion of HEAT in undergraduate programs, reinforcing the need for enhanced emergency preparedness. Gannon and Paraskevas (2017) further explored the challenges multinational corporations face in crisis response, emphasizing the ethical dilemmas surrounding employee security in hostile environments. Their research underscored the necessity of structured intervention protocols and corporate responsibility in managing workforce safety.

As illustrated in the table below, The Aid Worker Security Report 2023 highlights that in 2022, 444 humanitarian aid workers were affected by violence in 235 major attacks, resulting in 116 fatalities (Humanitarian Outcomes, 2023).

Table 1. Major Attacks on Aid Workers: Summary Statistics, 2018 – 2022

Category	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Number of Incidents	229	276	283	268	235
Total Aid Worker Victims	409	481	484	461	444
Total Injured	131	125	117	141	116

Security training in the humanitarian sector plays a vital role in preparing aid workers for high-risk environments, but significant disparities persist. The Aid Worker Security Report 2023 highlights how international staff often receive comprehensive security training, while national aid workers who face the highest risks struggle with limited access due to financial constraints, language barriers, and logistical challenges. Despite the growing use of HEAT, no standardized model exists, leading to inconsistent preparedness among aid workers. Additionally, while security training is widely accepted as necessary, its effectiveness in reducing casualties remains unproven. Most evaluations focus on

engagement rather than measurable security outcomes. Addressing these gaps requires defining clear outcome metrics, expanding training accessibility for national staff, and integrating diverse perspectives into training programs. Without these improvements, many frontline aid workers will remain inadequately prepared for the dangers they encounter in humanitarian crises (Humanitarian Outcomes, 2023).

Background of the Study

In high-risk environments, emergency responders face complex challenges requiring both medical proficiency and situational adaptability. Traditional emergency protocols often advocate a “stage and wait” approach, prioritizing personal safety before intervention. However, in volatile conditions, delaying medical aid can significantly impact survivability. HTEC equips first responders with critical medical intervention techniques, ensuring effective treatment in austere and high-threat situations. Meanwhile, HEAT develops situational awareness, survival strategies, and risk mitigation, preparing individuals to operate safely in hostile settings. The integration of these programs enables responders to balance risk assessment and urgent care, fostering an adaptive and proactive emergency response framework.

This study examines the combined impact of HTEC and HEAT on emergency response behaviors across diverse professions, including civilians, law enforcement officers, military personnel, and emergency rescue workers. Through survey and interview analyses, the research evaluates shifts in motivation, adaptability, and decision-making, assessing how integrated training enhances responder confidence, operational efficiency, and crisis preparedness.

Research Questions

1. How does the integration of HTEC and HEAT training influence participants' willingness to intervene in high-threat emergency scenarios?
2. How do personal safety concerns impact decision-making and response actions among trained individuals in crisis situations?
3. To what extent does HTEC-HEAT training facilitate a shift in mindset from passive waiting to proactive emergency intervention?

Research Objectives

1. Assess participant readiness to respond to high-threat situations following HTEC-HEAT training.
2. Analyze the role of safety concerns in shaping emergency response decisions and behaviors.
3. Evaluate mindset shifts regarding crisis intervention, comparing traditional "stage and wait" approaches to proactive strategies such as "care under fire".

The findings of this study will offer valuable insights for decision-makers and government agencies, aiming to enhance survivability by integrating sound medical principles with

effective tactical strategies.

Conceptual Framework: Integrating HTEC and HEAT in Emergency Response

This study integrates Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) (Rogers, 1983) with the combined training approach of HTEC and HEAT, examining how participants' decision-making and behavioral responses adapt in high-risk environments. The framework evaluates key training components, including tactical emergency care education, crisis response simulations, psychological preparedness, and situational awareness, emphasizing the transition from passive waiting to proactive intervention in hostile settings. PMT has been widely applied to understand behavioral responses to perceived threats. Shillair (2020) describes PMT as a framework for assessing responses triggered by fear-based messages, where individuals evaluate threats based on severity and vulnerability while simultaneously considering coping mechanisms such as response efficacy and self-efficacy. If the perceived threat outweighs an individual's coping mechanisms, maladaptive responses such as denial or avoidance may follow. Conversely, strong coping appraisals foster protection motivation and proactive emergency intervention. Building on this, Farooq et al. (2019) applied PMT and the Theory of Planned Behavior to analyze security behaviors, highlighting self-efficacy as a major factor influencing intervention willingness. Their findings indicated that attitude and confidence are critical in shaping behavioral responses, whereas perceived vulnerability and response cost were less impactful.

By integrating PMT with HTEC and HEAT, this study highlights the importance of structured intervention strategies, crisis preparedness, and tactical response efficiency. The fusion of medical training (HTEC) and environmental risk awareness (HEAT) fosters higher self-efficacy, operational confidence, and resilience, ensuring more effective emergency decision-making in hostile environments.

Below is a visual presentation of the conceptual framework, illustrating the relationships between HTEC and HEAT training, mediating factors, and behavioral outcomes in emergency response scenarios.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for HTEC and HEAT Emergency Response

This study integrates HTEC and HEAT training with PMT to enhance emergency readiness, risk assessment, and tactical response, fostering proactive intervention, situational awareness, and operational confidence in high-threat scenarios.

METHODOLOGY

This research examines the joint impact of HTEC and HEAT training on emergency responders, employing a mixed-method approach to assess motivation, adaptability, and crisis decision-making. The survey instrument, titled survey on participants' motivation and adaptive response in HTEC-HEAT training, consists of eight questions divided into two sections: demographics and attitudes toward operational risks and decision-making in crisis scenarios. This structured assessment ensures a comprehensive understanding of situational awareness, medical proficiency, and tactical response in high-threat environments. Data collection was conducted in collaboration with Pilipinas 911, led by Mr. Ruel S. Kapunan, the HTEC lead trainer.

Additionally, the study applies PMT (Rogers, 1983), which explores how individuals assess threats and decide to take preventive actions based on threat appraisal (perceived severity, vulnerability, and rewards) and coping appraisal (self-efficacy, response efficacy, and response cost).

RESULTS

Data for the study were gathered through the administration of a created survey instrument. The first 5 items of the survey were constructed to establish a demographic background for the participants involved in this research. There were 44 respondents.

As illustrated in Table 2 there were 95% male respondents and 5% female respondents.

Table 2. Sex

Items	Total	Percentage
Male	42	95%
Female	4	5%

As to age, 54% or half of respondent's age are from 35-44 years old, there were 31% respondents who are 25-35 years old and 13% are from 45-54 years old.

Table 3. Age

Items	Total	Percentage
45-54 years old	6	13%
35-44 years old	24	54%
25-35 years old	14	31%

As to occupation, 45% respondent's works in a private company, 40% were government employee, and the remaining 7% are retired from private and government service.

Table 4. Occupation

Items	Total	Percentage
Retired	2	7%
Private	22	45%
Government	20	40%

Law enforcement and emergency rescue professionals each make up 18% of respondents, highlighting strong participation in high-threat response operations. Medical professionals (13%) and security personnel (14%) play key roles in emergency preparedness. Other professions, including administrative staff, Information Technology (IT) officers, and engineers, contribute essential skills for effective crisis management.

Table 5. Profession

Items	Total	Percentage
Law Enforcement	8	18%
Emergency Rescue	8	18%
Medical	6	13%
IT Officer	4	9%
Engineer	4	9%
Security	6	14%
Administrative	8	9%

As to educational attainment, 77% of the respondents are bachelor's degree graduate, 13% who were master's degree graduate and the remaining 10% of respondents are with doctoral degree.

Table 6. Education

Items	Total	Percentage
Doctoral	4	10%
Masteral	6	13%
Bachelor	34	77%

The second part of the survey examines participants' willingness, concerns, and mindset shifts in responding to high-threat emergencies, emphasizing the need for structured HTEC and HEAT training, enhanced situational awareness, and coordinated intervention to improve emergency response effectiveness.

Table 7. Emergency Response Readiness: HTEC-HEAT Training Results

Category	Agree (count)	Agree (%)	Disagree (count)	Disagree (%)
Willingness to intervene in high-threat scenarios	40	91%	4	9%
Concerned about safety in high-threat responses	35	80%	9	20%
Agrees to shift mindset to proactive response	38	86%	6	14%

The survey results from 44 respondents indicate a high level of willingness to intervene in high-threat emergency scenarios, with 91% (40 respondents) ready to act despite potential dangers. This strong agreement suggests that most participants recognize the importance of immediate response and feel adequately prepared to assist. However, 9% (4 respondents) expressed hesitation, emphasizing concerns about personal safety, situational risks, and the need for structured intervention protocols.

Regarding concerns about personal safety, 80% (35 respondents) acknowledged the risks involved and emphasized the necessity of protective measures to ensure responder safety. These concerns highlight the importance of proper training, situational awareness, and collaboration with emergency teams to minimize risks and enable safer intervention strategies. Meanwhile, 20% (9 respondents) identified personal security as a key barrier, reinforcing the need for clear operational guidelines before engaging in crisis situations.

A significant portion of participants 86% (38 respondents) agreed that shifting from a passive to a proactive emergency response mindset is critical for effective intervention. Their support indicates a growing recognition of the value of hands-on training, real-world simulation exercises, and structured coordination with law enforcement and medical teams. On the other hand, 14% (6 respondents) preferred a more cautious approach, suggesting that further education and experience may be necessary to instill confidence in high-threat response scenarios.

Overall, these findings illustrate HEAT's alignment with HTEC principles, highlighting the importance of continuous education, real-world simulations, and interdisciplinary collaboration. By refining intervention strategies, these training programs contribute to safer and more resilient emergency response frameworks in hostile environments.

DISCUSSION

The survey results indicate a strong willingness among participants to intervene in high-threat emergency situations, with most expressing readiness to act despite potential dangers. The integration of HTEC and HEAT training fosters situational awareness, tactical medical proficiency, and crisis adaptability, equipping responders to manage volatile environments effectively. However, concerns about personal safety persist, highlighting the need for enhanced protective measures, structured intervention protocols, and continuous education. Regarding safety concerns, respondents emphasized the importance of risk assessment, threat mitigation, and operational coordination with emergency teams, law enforcement, and medical personnel to ensure effective intervention while minimizing risks. Some viewed personal security as a key barrier, reinforcing the necessity for clear crisis response strategies before engagement. A significant number of respondents supported transitioning from passive waiting to proactive intervention, recognizing the benefits of real-world simulations, interdisciplinary collaboration, and tactical preparedness in improving emergency response efficiency. However, some preferred a more cautious approach, indicating that additional training and experience may be required to build confidence in high-threat scenarios.

These findings underscore the importance of integrating HTEC's medical response framework with HEAT's situational awareness training, ensuring a resilient emergency response system through education, simulation-based learning, and enhanced crisis preparedness.

Conclusions

The findings highlight the joint impact of HTEC and HEAT training, demonstrating how structured intervention improves emergency readiness, risk assessment, and tactical response. While most participants expressed willingness to intervene in high-threat situations, concerns about personal safety remain significant. To address these challenges, integrating HTEC's medical intervention techniques with HEAT's situational awareness training ensures effective crisis management and risk mitigation. Proper coordination between civilians, emergency teams, and law enforcement enhances safety and operational efficiency. Future initiatives should focus on continuous education, real-

world simulations, and interdisciplinary collaboration, reinforcing confidence and adaptability in responders while building a resilient and capable community equipped for hostile environments.

Recommendations

This paper emphasizes the joint impact of HTEC and HEAT, highlighting the need for expanded training, structured safety protocols, and real-world simulations to enhance emergency preparedness and tactical response. While most participants are willing to intervene, concerns about personal safety remain a significant factor in decision-making.

Integrating HTEC's medical intervention principles with HEAT's situational awareness strategies ensures effective crisis management while minimizing risks. Strengthening coordination between trained civilians, emergency teams, and law enforcement improves response efficiency in high-threat environments. These recommendations collectively support a capable, resilient community of responders, ensuring effective intervention in hostile environments while improving survival rates and operational confidence.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper strictly adheres to ethical research standards. The author obtained respondents' consent during the survey process, clearly explaining the study's purpose and ensuring the confidentiality of their identities. The author hereby declare that artificial intelligence was used solely for checking grammar and syntax.

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